

21ST CENTURY CHALLENGE: THERMAL MANAGEMENT DESIGN REQUIREMENTS

Larry C. Jenkins, Abigail Bennett, USAF Aeronautical System Center

Abstract

As we enter the 21st century the system engineering challenge of thermal management of digital avionics is intensifying. The functional need for faster, smaller devices is pressing systems to their mechanical and physical limits. At present thermal management is widely seen as a secondary issue, needed only for reliability of components. The goal of this paper is to show that thermal management is becoming more than a reliability factor in digital avionics. It is a fundamental driver in the development of the architecture for advance designs. Thermal design is integral in meeting the functional design requirements of systems, especially as the drive to lower cost move systems to use more common commercial devices and subsystems. This paper will address some of the impacts this design process has on avionics system performance, and how these impacts affect the system engineering requirements of the air vehicle. Thermal management must be an integral part of the air vehicle and avionic systems design to insure system engineering success.

The goal of this paper is to give a clearer picture of the challenges we face in addressing thermal management issues. One topic that will be explored is how functional performance can be severely compromised in systems where the design is driven primarily by TM. We need to better understand the dynamics of trading weight which may be directly linked to the thermal management challenge. We want to show the relevance of thermal management design requirements to architecture development of avionics systems. To get the best system the entire dynamic picture of how thermal management ties in, with electrical and physical design is needed to achieve the desired efficiency and effectiveness in the 21st century systems.

Introduction

Avionics requirements are becoming more challenging and technically demanding with turn

cycles reduce to months instead of years. The drive to exceed current technological limitations and the race to progress endures in both the military and commercial world. Market pressures and commoditization of commercial products are forcing innovation and rapid market turns to ensure economic success. Military needs also press the challenge of avionics design by consistently requesting quantum leaps in speed, accuracy, and functional performance while engaging in cost cutting measures with the use of COTS (commercial of the shelf) equipment. These market conditions are creating an interesting challenge in the design and development process of present and future systems. This drive to design avionics systems in a short time frame exacerbates the challenge associated with thermal management.

Section I

The challenge of thermal management has traditionally been treated by avionics designers as a secondary issue, beyond their area of concern, to be addressed by mechanical and packaging engineers. While pressing forward with electrical design, avionics engineers focus on selecting de-rated parts and devices as a means to ensure thermal concerns are addressed along with reliability issues. This discrete and often divisive approach persisted into the 70s and 80s, but the flaw in this process has become apparent in products for both commercial and military enterprises. Therefore, a concerted effort has taken place to ensure a more integral system engineering approach takes place. Many of today's leaders in avionics development have moved away from this position of thermal management being a secondary issue and towards a system approach where thermal management design is an integral part of the process in establishing an effective design. A design focusing on the best balance from an energy and mass interchange perspective is the goal. The impact and importance of thermal management in the system engineering process is enabling industry to create truly effective functional designs. This system engineering

approach is also linked to minimizing cost and to development of an effective life cycle cost process. The thermal management challenge is tied to the overall system requirement challenge which attempts to ensure a balance can be achieved in performance and life versus cost. Both military and commercial enterprises are looking for this balance between functional performance and life integrity which is driven by the merit of cost and field performance. Neither industry nor the military can afford failure in finding this balance because it can mean the life or death of a product or more importantly the life or death of an American soldier.

In order to find this balance in a design from a system and thermal management view point we need to take a look at the system engineering process being employed today. The thermal management challenge needs to become integral to the system synthesis and design optimization process to effectively make an impact on overall life cycle cost. Today in seeking success in the system design challenge, weight is often given a premium position as being the driving technical performance measurand that is used to show a design is moving in the right direction. Weight is a universal technical performance measure, integral to all avionic system design processes. This parameter is a benchmark for system development in the aviation industry because it can be directly linked to aeronautical performance. A constant tracking of weight is imbedded in the design process. Yet, the impact of mass or weight change on energy transfer in a system is looked at as a fallout effect of the avionics system with limited understanding of the ramifications at the air vehicle level. These changes in mass and weight can often change the characteristics of the components from a functional and electrical design perspective. The change in weight may directly affect how a system responds to thermal stress, impacting the functional profile of the electrical circuit as well as the long term integrity of the system from a reliability perspective.

The weight parameter is well understood by all parties in the business of avionics design, but the energy transfer affects which create the need for further thermal management may not be as easily delineated or understood. Thereby, gaps in knowledge exist in how best to perform the same

fidelity of analysis for thermal management as takes place for weight. The impacts of the two parameters weight and thermal management may be the same, but knowledge to evaluate the difference or change needs is often bounded by the understandings associated solely associated with weight or mass change.

Here's a simple example to bring evidence to this difference in impact on design and system requirement process. If you were building a simple radar system using five major subsystems as the primary construct or architecture system for a bid on a military aircraft you would be asked to meet some weight limit as a requirement driver. You may even receive an incentive in the contract to lower the weight impact by some percentage as means of encouraging critical work in this area. Immediately, the team works the functional requirements for performance and goes through trade studies to look at means for lowering the weight, often time finding success in packaging approaches and potential material changes to become more weight efficient. This activity for weight change would be a natural part of the design process in the system development with special emphasis and visibility. Limited resistance from any team members would arise in this process. All participants including the ultimate customer would see this work as a valuable design practice for avionics development and good for air vehicle design because they have knowledge and an understanding of the merit of this activity. On the other hand if we look at the full effect of this activity, the loss of mass or weight becomes a direct assault on the ability of the system to perform thermal management activities which directly relates to energy transfer in being a functional radar system. The loss in weight exacerbates the thermal management challenge because we impact the systems ability to transfer energy. Maybe too simple an example to generate any interest but today's electronic phase array radars are highly dependent on the effects of thermal management as much as the design is dependent on weight to be successful. Effective and efficient designers understand this interconnection and are seeking to work closure with their air vehicle customers to achieve the best valued design for the air vehicle. The imperative to reduce weight may also turn into a direct boost in power and thermal design impact

that requires work and possible weight gain outside the domain of the avionics system. This simple example profile may be stating the obvious, but it defines the challenge for avionics design in the 21st century. This design challenge is forcing us to discover better means for providing a true mass and energy exchange which ensures the desired functional performance and integrity desired.

Section II

In this section we will take a closer look at the challenge of TM as it relates to the performance of radar system components. Today's radar systems are more powerful than ever and are demanded to be both precise and reliable, especially for military applications. The heat flux for these systems is starting to expand beyond the range of 100 w/cm² which becomes a material challenge point for today's semi-conduction material like silicon and GaAs. In order to get optimum performance in these systems, it is imperative that the environment in which they operate is properly conditioned. Devices used in radar phased array systems are highly sensitive and must operate in a small temperature band to ensure consistent output power. One type of component which is particularly affected by temperature fluctuations is oscillators. A radar receiver with a local oscillator is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. W-Band Receiver with Local Oscillator [2]

Oscillation is the act of generating RF power without any RF input. Power oscillators in general are not very efficient in converting dc to RF power. In the conversion process, dc power that is not converted to RF energy is dissipated as heat. Oscillators are very small and can give off large quantities of heat energy which leads to high power dissipation densities. Proper thermal conditioning, to provide thermal stability, is critical to minimize fluctuations in an oscillator's output power level and frequency because its thermal impedance is a function of its temperature. The following passage quantifies the thermal stability constraint for oscillators and explains why this requirement is needed.

“Many oscillator design specifications require performance stability over a wide temperature range. Frequency stability requirements of 10 kHz/deg C are not uncommon. Performance variations result from two temperature-dependent effects: the fundamental changes in the device's semiconductor characteristics and from the expansion or contraction of the oscillator housing. When the cavity dimensions change, so does the resonant frequency. Copper expands at -15 ppm/°C, which results in a 150 kHz change in frequency at X-band. If the cavity Q is high, such thermal expansion will be the primary cause of frequency drift. If the cavity Q is low changes in the semiconductor characteristics are the primary contributor to frequency drift. The semiconductor device is stable over a narrow temperature range (20degC); its RF output power decreases or increases outside this range. Stable output power can be maintained only by holding device temperature constant. [1]”

Other elements in phased array radar systems that are affected by temperature fluctuations are phase shifters. Phase shifters are used to direct the radar in the desired direction by controlling wavefront formation (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Phase Steering [2]

Because each array uses thousands of electronic phase shifters, the operating characteristics of these components have a profound affect on the performance and cost of the radar. One parameter that can affect the systems ability to steer the radar is phase shift error. Phase shift error can occur due to variations of frequency, phase state, power and temperature. "Phase error reduces the antenna gain in a transmitting array and raises sidelobes in a receiving array. [3]" When considering a large number of phase shifters, the calculation of this error may include variations from unit to unit. If each module assumed a different

temperature, thus different phase relative to surrounding modules, it would be impossible to predict array beam forming characteristics.

These are only two examples why TM is important for advanced avionic systems. If TM considerations are not part of the early design process, high performance radar might not provide optimum capabilities because its environment is not properly controlled.

Section III

In section three we move back to the system engineering process to look at the best approach for addressing this challenge of TM which is critical to development of avionics. We have established the fact that TM is directly linked to functional performance of avionic systems especially in the area of radar systems. We now want to address the synthesis portion of the system engineering process where the functional requirements are being transformed to physical architecture and system configuration for balance. The balance sought at this reference point is the balance of cost, performance, and time. As noted in Figure 3 below a generic profile of a System engineering process highlights the synthesis process step as an area where physical interfaces are refined and defined, and this point of reference links us to the challenge point for TM design activities.

Figure 3. System Engineering Process Chart

Today's avionic designer's primary focus during this phase of system engineering usually focus on weight and functionality as the balance factor in meeting design requirements. This condition often leads to interface requirements which can become overwhelming on the side of the thermal control system or the environmental control system community which interfaces or supports the avionics. This challenge point then moves to an arena outside the contractual profile of the avionics community which works well for them but does not always provide the best solution from an overall air vehicle perspective. This condition is not a malicious or crass activity by avionic developers but a fact of life in the business world. Industry works within a defined controlled design space to provide the best possible products but the element effects of thermal management need to be understood and incorporated in process. This means that the system engineering and interfacing activities need to be employed early in the process to ensure success. In order to produce the best system of balance at the highest level of assembly more front end work is required in the system engineering step of synthesis to minimize cost impacts and maximize the opportunity for creating an effective and efficient design. This interaction of weight to thermal management has already been explored based on the radar example so the following can be suggested:

Critical to all weight studies a parallel study to assess thermal management impacts on design at the component and system level should be implemented

Weight changes from a positive viewpoint should be studied as a part of system level trade off studies. Weight is always looked at as a penalty factor in the aviation industry when the mass associated with weight may be the key to thermal management stability.

Alternatives to performance versus weight and thermal management should be provided to customer as a trading point early in design to insure priorities of design are understood by all parties

Multi-level research should be performed to look at this basic interaction link between weights or mass properties change and energy transfer in avionics.

These suggestions are a starting point for the enhancement of the system design process for developing avionics for air vehicles. For military applications these moves are an imperative if we are to meet our global mission requirements as a war fighting community. The additional drive by the military for greater design integrity with minimum cost impact by employing COTS exacerbates the design challenge. Therefore, this need for improve activities in the avionics world is not limited to military activities but also links back to the issue of commoditized and generalized electronic devices being produced for the global market. COTS integration into advance systems and many of today's sustainment activities will have to address this challenge in order to assure success.

To reinforce the importance of thermal management in the system design process review Figure 4. Figure 4 shows that 55% of electronic components failures in industry are caused by temperature effects.

Figure 4. Major Cause of Electronic Failure [4]

This simple impact on components readily indicates the high potential for being a design driver. If we just assume vibration represents the mechanical challenges of design and are directly linked to weight; this percentage impact would be 20% which is less than half the impact of temperature. This approach may be a conservative push for weight relation to vibration but it does emphatically show the disparity between weight and TM being a driver in the design for performance. Historically, this assessment was the driver behind making sure you picked de-rated components to compensate for thermal impacts to

ensure design goals were achieved for your assembly or circuit. This practice is still used today but the thermal impact on circuits' Tj (junction temperature) is even more sensitive. Packaging engineers are moving away from de-rating as the only set approach and looking into the direct design factors at the die level and micro-level to insure success of the device. This parameter of Tj is also becoming a critical economic factor in the processor business. Recently, at the 2004 Intersociety Thermal Phenomena (ITHERM) Conference an Intel representative expressed the concern that a ½ degree change in junction was worth millions in terms of market impact. This sensitivity to temperature in the design of critical electronic components indicates the need for additional attention of TM in the system design process. The market position indicated by this statement made by Intel directly links to an impact on military systems which utilize COTS technology. This condition challenges the multitude of activities taking place in the development of advance systems using processing chips and components from the open market. This reinforces our argument that TM is a critical parameter of design which needs to start taking more priority in the system design process.

Conclusion

The key to the future of avionic developments is the integration of TM into the system design and development engineering process. The basic physics of addressing the weight parameter in design is directly linked to the TM challenge. Removal or change of weight changes the basic physics of the materials involved in the electrical circuit process and this effect directly impacts the thermal stress of the devices employed in the electrical circuit function. The realization of this condition moves the priority of the TM challenge to the forefront making it a critical focus for the 21st century development of avionics.

Future studies should be performed on this area of challenge to greater inform the industry on the driving importance of integrating and making TM more visible and appreciated in the system requirements and optimization process for avionics. In the global markets for components Asian developers are exploring the aforementioned

approaches to this challenge and the success could make conditions monopolistic if western markets do not join in the fight against this challenge of the 21st century. The understanding of the thermal phenomena mechanisms at the device level is still a vast area needing study and advancement in research and practical applications.

The critical need for this approach in system engineering for cost avoidance and savings is supported by the big picture viewpoint on the system engineering process studied by NASA (National Aeronautical and Space Administration). A NASA study evaluated the effects of system engineering investment on the front end relative to cost overruns on the back end of the process from production through to life sustainment end of development. The NASA report states the following: "projects that expended the industry average of 2% to 3% of total project cost/effort on the (full life cycle) requirements process experienced an 80% to 200% cost overrun, while projects that invested 8% to 14% of total project cost/effort in the requirements process had 0% to 50% overruns. [5]" This reinforces the point that more investment needs to be made in TM design for avionics in the 21st century to insure continued success from a market perspective as well as security and defense. Investment in the TM challenge will provide return to the design and system engineering process from a physical perspective and economic perspective giving designers and customers a truly balanced system for the 21st century. Economic value and system integrated performance results will be achieved and merited using this approach.

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